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Starter Kits for Professional Networks

Data Steward

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
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Starter Kits for Professional Networks

Data Steward

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Terminology

Terminology / Acronym	Definition
Community	A mutually supportive, self-perpetuating group with purpose and structure.
Community Canvas	A framework designed to help build and run a new community, or analyse and improve an existing one by identifying fundamental themes of identity, experience, and structure.
Community of practice	A group who shares a common concern, set of problems, or interest in a topic and who come together to fulfil individual and group goals.
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement.
CSCCE Community Participation Model	A framework for modes of member engagement occurring in a community: convey/consume, collaborate, co-create, and outside of it: champion.
Data Steward	Data stewards cover expertise in managing research objects for sharing with the scientific community and the public.
DSIG	Data Stewards Interest Group.

See also EOSC Glossary: <https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

1. Introduction

This handbook is a condensed version of the *Data Steward Network Starter Kit* (Horton et al., 2023). It supports the creation, launch, and development of new professional and sustainable communities of practice in the field of data stewardship.

Professional networks play a key role in the context of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, where they are considered tools for lifelong learning through peer exchange.

This document brings together theoretical models and practical action points to help data stewards build and develop their communities effectively.

2. Conceptual Foundations: three models for building communities

This starter kit draws on three complementary models of community organisation. Each provides a different lens to understand, plan, and support a professional network — and together they offer a flexible and robust foundation for community building.

2.1 Community of Practice

(Trayner & Trayner, 2015)

A Community of Practice is a group of people who share a concern or passion for something they do — and who learn how to do it better through regular interaction.

Three key characteristics define a Community of Practice:

DOMAIN

A shared identity around a common domain of interest. This defines the scope of the community and implies both commitment and shared competence.

(e.g. data stewardship, FAIR principles, metadata standards...)

COMMUNITY

A group that builds relationships and supports mutual learning. Members are invested in the community and motivated to apply what they learn in practice.

PRACTICE

A shared repertoire of experiences, tools, stories, challenges, and solutions — built over time through collaboration and dialogue.

Communities of Practice are particularly relevant for smaller or informal groups with strong peer interaction and shared professional challenges.

2.2 CSCCE Community Participation Model

(Woodley & Pratt, 2020)

The Community Participation Model, developed by the CSCCE (Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement), offers a framework to understand how members engage with a community and how information flows.

It defines four participation modes:

CONVEY / CONSUME

Information flows from community leads to members. Members are listeners or readers.

“Here is something interesting.”

CONTRIBUTE

Members provide input, feedback, or resources, but don't co-create.

“Give us your perspective.”

COLLABORATE

Members work together, exchange ideas, and learn from each other.

“How can we work together?”

CO-CREATE

Members and leads jointly create content, activities, or strategies.

“Let's build this together.”

An additional role — Champion — exists outside the community, where members advocate or represent the group externally.

This model is especially useful for designing inclusive communities that support members at different levels of engagement and commitment.

2.3 Community Canvas

(Community Canvas Collective, 2017)

The Community Canvas is a practical framework to help design, launch, and sustain a community.

It is structured around three core themes:

IDENTITY

Defines the community's purpose, values, goals, and target members.

Why do we exist? What do we believe in?

EXPERIENCE

Shapes how people interact and participate — including communication channels, onboarding, events, and rules of engagement.

STRUCTURE

Covers governance, roles, resources, processes, and sustainability mechanisms.

The Community Canvas provides templates and questions to help clarify strategic choices and operational needs.

It is particularly helpful during the launch and growth phases of a community, supporting both short- and long-term planning.

Three Models for Building Communities

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

Learning through shared practice

- Focus: Domain, Community, Practice
- Builds shared identity and peer learning
- Answers: "How do we learn together?"

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION MODEL

Modes of engagement and information flow

- Participation types: Convey, Contribute, Collaborate, Co-create
- Includes external role: Champion
- Answers: "How do members engage and contribute?"

COMMUNITY CANVAS

Designing identity, experience, and structure

- Framework: Identity, Experience, Structure
- Supports planning, roles, communication
- Answers: "Who are we, what do we do, and how are we organised?"

2.4 The Three Phases of Community Development

The practical application of the models described above takes place over three main phases in the life of a community:

Getting Started, Launch, and Sustain.

While each community follows its own rhythm, these phases provide a useful structure to think through planning, coordination, and long-term development.

The infographic below provides a visual overview of this lifecycle.

Visual timeline of the three main phases:
 ⇒ GETTING STARTED ⇒ LAUNCH ⇒ SUSTAIN

3. Getting Started

This section outlines the essential steps to consider before launching a community or network. It helps define purpose, identify benefits, understand potential members, and begin shaping structure and responsibilities.

3.1 Identify purpose and benefits

Start by asking:

Why should this community exist, and who is it for?

- A well-defined purpose will help shape priorities, attract engagement, and guide strategic decisions.
- Benefits for the community and its members may include:
 - Addressing shared challenges through collaborative problem-solving;
 - Sharing expertise and lessons learned;
 - Identifying gaps in practices, tools, or policies;
 - Amplifying concerns across institutions or sectors.

3.2 Understand your potential members

Who do you want to involve – and how?

Take time to understand the needs, interests, and capacities of potential members. Consider:

- Online surveys to assess interest and availability;
- Informal interviews or focus groups;
- Group discussions during existing events or workshops.
- This helps define your audience and tailor the structure and activities of the community accordingly.

Key Actions per Phase

PHASE 1 ⇒ GETTING STARTED

- Identify purpose and benefits
- Understand your potential members
- Community or network?
- Refer to models to guide your planning
- Define early roles

PHASE 2 ⇒ LAUNCH

- Review the landscape
- Define your domain of interest
- Use structured planning tools
- Set ground rules and inclusion principles
- Identify initial leads and champions
- Establish communication and infrastructure
- Host a kick-off
- Promote and grow

PHASE 3 ⇒ SUSTAIN

- Anticipate evolution
- Understand member engagement levels
- Address barriers to participation
- Make roles and team composition visible
- Maintain energy and commitment
- Reflect and adapt
- Manage transitions
- Prevent group dysfunction
- Keep purpose alive

4. Launch

Once you have defined the purpose of your community and understood your potential members, the next step is to plan and carry out the launch. This involves clarifying structure, setting expectations, initiating communication, and building momentum through a first event or activity.

4.1 Review the landscape

Are you duplicating something that already exists? Or could you partner with others?

Before creating something new, take stock of existing communities or forums. If similar initiatives already exist, consider how your effort could complement rather than compete with them.

4.2 Define your domain of interest

Clarify the scope and focus of your community. Ask questions such as:

- What need or gap are we addressing?
- What topics are likely to attract sustained interest?
- What will be lost if this community does not exist?
- This helps sharpen the community's identity and value proposition.

4.3 Use structured planning tools

Apply elements of the Community Canvas to define:

- Identity and purpose
- Core values
- Goals and success metrics
- Decision-making processes
- Roles and expectations

These help create clarity and shared understanding from the beginning.

4.4 Set ground rules and inclusion principles

How do we make the community a safe and welcoming space?

Draft a Code of Conduct and consider writing a simple charter that includes:

- Membership criteria
- Behavioural expectations
- Principles of diversity, equity, and inclusion
- Norms for collaboration and confidentiality

4.5 Identify initial leads and champions

Select or invite individuals who will:

- **Leads** – coordinate, set direction, and guide early activities;
- **Champions** – promote the initiative, engage new members, and help grow the network.

Refer to the CSCCE Community Participation Model to think about the different skillsets and levels of engagement that might be needed.

4.6 Establish communication and infrastructure

How will people connect, communicate, and collaborate?

Choose your initial communication channels (e.g. email lists, Slack, Discord) and define how documentation will be shared (e.g. repositories, shared drives, wikis).

Plan for regular interactions to encourage discussion, feedback, and knowledge sharing.

4.7 Host a kick-off

The kick-off meeting is your opportunity to:

- Gather members around shared goals;
- Introduce leads and champions;
- Present the community's purpose and scope;

- Establish behavioural norms and expectations;
- Launch initial discussions or collaborative activities.

This can be in person, online, or hybrid — depending on the profile and availability of your members.

4.8 Promote and grow

Use diverse channels to promote the community:

- Internal communications;
- Social media;
- Newsletters;
- Relevant conferences or public events.

Promotion is not just visibility — it's outreach, inclusion, and invitation.

As interest grows, make it easy for people to join, contribute, and find value in participating.

5. Sustain

After the launch, sustaining a community means more than keeping it alive — it's about nurturing participation, enabling evolution, and ensuring that both individual and collective value continue to grow over time.

This section outlines practical steps to support long-term engagement, address common challenges, and plan for the community's ongoing development.

5.1 Anticipate evolution

Communities are not static — their composition, goals, and dynamics change over time. Members join and leave; roles shift; motivations evolve.

Build in flexibility and revisit goals and structures periodically to ensure continued relevance.

5.2 Understand member engagement levels

Refer to the Community Participation Model to map out different levels of engagement:

- **Core** – leads, organisers, deeply involved members;
- **Active** – regular contributors;
- **Occasional** – contributors with lower frequency;
- **Peripheral** – members who observe or participate passively.

Encourage movement between levels. A dynamic balance across types of engagement keeps the community healthy.

5.3 Address barriers to participation

Use scaffolding strategies to support inclusion and accessibility:

- Onboarding guides or welcome sessions;
- Technical support for communication tools;
- Templates for note-taking or presentations
- Opportunities for informal social interaction;
- Feedback mechanisms (e.g. surveys, check-ins).

These actions lower the barrier to entry and help members feel confident in contributing.

5.4 Make roles and team composition visible

Use tools like the Belbin Team Roles (2010) or your own mappings to identify:

- Strengths in the group;
- Gaps in roles or perspectives;
- Preferences and boundaries.

Support members in finding roles that match their motivation and availability.

5.5 Maintain energy and commitment

Sustained participation often relies on a mix of:

- Learning opportunities (e.g. training, peer exchange);
- Recognition (e.g. shout-outs, credits, acknowledgements);
- Networking and visibility (e.g. presenting at events, publishing outcomes).

People stay engaged when they find value and feel valued.

5.6 Reflect and adapt

Regularly assess:

- Whether members feel their needs are being met;
- Whether goals still align with community activity;
- Which obstacles are emerging.

Use this input to refine programming, formats, or even governance structures.

5.7 Manage transitions

People leave communities — and that's normal.

What matters is to:

- Welcome newcomers effectively (onboarding);
- Acknowledge departures (offboarding);
- Plan for leadership succession, especially for leads and champions;
- Preserve knowledge, using shared documentation or mentoring.

Sustainable communities plan for change — they don't just react to it.

5.8 Prevent group dysfunction

Watch for common group dynamics that can harm participation:

- **Social loafing** – when some members rely on others to do the work;
- **Free riding** – benefiting without contributing;
- **Groupthink** – suppressing dissent for harmony;
- **Exclusion** – whether intentional or accidental.

Build a culture of awareness, openness, and shared responsibility.

5.9 Keep purpose alive

Communities may outlive their original scope — or reach natural endpoints.

That's why it's essential to:

- Revisit the original purpose;
- Acknowledge what has been achieved;
- Discuss future directions, or even closure, if appropriate.

Ending a community is not failure. It can be the result of success, transformation, or responsible resource management.

Key Roles per Phase Across the Community Lifecycle

PHASE 1 ⇒ GETTING STARTED

Defines scope and coordinates planning

Promotes the idea and builds early interest

PHASE 2 ⇒ LAUNCH

Facilitates launch activities and defines structure

Recruits members and energizes the community

Moderates the kick-off meeting and guides interaction

PHASE 3 ⇒ SUSTAIN

Monitors progress and enables succession

Supports growth and strategic evolution

Runs meetings

Archivist:
preserves knowledge

Communicator:
manages external messaging

Belbin-style roles:
e.g. Shaper, Completer, Team Worker

6. Conclusion

This handbook provides a structured pathway for building, launching, and sustaining a professional community or network in the field of data stewardship.

By combining conceptual models with practical actions, it supports community leads, champions, and members in:

- defining clear objectives and values;
- fostering engagement and participation;
- ensuring long-term relevance and resilience.

Whether you are just getting started or looking to grow an existing initiative, these tools can help you build something meaningful, inclusive, and sustainable — together.

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